

SESQUITERPENES AND RELATED SUBSTANCES. PART IV. SYNTHESIS OF A STRUCTURAL ISOMER OF THE DICARBOXYLIC ACID, $C_{11}H_{16}O_4$ *, A DEGRADATION PRODUCT OF CEDRENE

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1:3-Trimethylcyclohexane-2:4-dicarboxylic acid was synthesised with a view to comparing its properties with a C_{11} -dicarboxylic acid, a degradation product of cedrene, and these were found to be different.

Through a series of oxidative degradations on cedrene, a dicarboxylic acid, $C_{11}H_{16}O_4$, was isolated (Plattner *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1943, **26**, 1553). As a result of further degradative work on this acid, its constitution was suggested to be one of the following (Plattner *et al.*, *Chimia*, 1948, **2**, 248; *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, **36**, 1845).

More recently, the structure of cedrene has been completely elucidated from degradative and synthetic standpoints (Plattner *et al.*, *loc. cit.*; Stork *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 3291; 1955, **77**, 1073) and the structure (II) of the C_{11} -acid has been fully established.

Experiments described herein were carried out in 1948-49 and dealt with the synthesis of the acid represented by structure (I). The properties of this synthetic acid were, however, found to be quite different from that isolated from the natural source.

α -Dicyano- β -dimethylglutarimide was condensed with 1:3-dibromobutane (Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **106**, 1356) in alcoholic solution. The condensation can proceed efficiently in different ways and the final condensation product is found to depend considerably on the duration of refluxing of the reaction mixture. If the refluxing period is limited to about 8 hours, a considerable quantity of a crystalline material separates out from the reaction mixture on dilution with acidulated water, from which the desired condensation product (III) can be isolated in about 5% yield by repeated crystallisations. The crystalline material recovered from the mother-liquor probably contains, in addition to (III), an unsaturated compound, most probably (IVa) and/or a bromo compound (IVb) which have been formed through the normal condensation of the primary bromine and

* This investigation was carried out in 1948-49 during the tenure of a foreign travelling Fellowship awarded by the University of Calcutta in 1947 and constituted a part of the report submitted to the University.

** Cf. Plattner *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, **36**, 1849, foot note 2.

with or without the elimination of the secondary bromine. This view has been arrived at mainly from a study of the hydrolysis results. If the period of refluxing be extended to 24 hours, the yield of the crystalline material decreases considerably. Attempts at acidic hydrolysis of the imide (III) being not very promising, it was hydrolysed by refluxing with alkali. The tetracarboxylic acid (V) was decarboxylated in the usual way and the oily acid, so obtained, was isolated as its anhydride (VI). The properties of the synthetic anhydride and also I.R. studies show considerable divergence from the anhydride of the C_{11} -acid.

To characterise the synthetic product further, it was hydrolysed to the acid (I) which was an oil at room temperature, but solidified to small needle-shaped crystals, when cooled in ice. This was converted into *p*-bromophenacyl derivative, which separated from the reaction mixture in about 60% yield in a quite pure form, and from which only one form of crystals was isolated. It appears that the anhydride is quite homogeneous in nature.

The nature and constitution of the products (IVa) and/or (IVb) have been arrived at in an indirect way. Because of the very close similarity with (III), these could not be prepared in a very pure state. On alkaline hydrolysis, the impure product afforded a mixture of crystalline acids, which on thermal degradation was treated with acetic anhydride. On distillation, a low-boiling acidic fraction has been isolated along with a higher boiling product which has been identified as the anhydride (VI). The lower-boiling fraction was warmed with alkali to remove any acetic anhydride and was finally purified by distillation. The analytical values correspond to that of an unsaturated hexoic acid. It takes up one molecule of hydrogen catalytically. The saturated acid has been characterised by its anilide and other physical properties and is found to be identical with hexoic acid. The unsaturated acid is found to develop a strong yellow coloration with tetranitromethane; it furnishes an anilide melting at 85° and which corresponds to the anilide of Δ^7 -hexenoic acid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 204). The anilide of Δ^6 -acid melts at 55° . The following sequence of reactions can explain easily the formation of hexenoic acid (VIII) due to the reversal of the Michael addition process in presence of alkali.

Since $\beta\beta$ -dimethylacrylic acid decomposes into butylene and carbon dioxide at about 205° , it is quite natural that during decarboxylation at 200° - 210° , this component is lost, and from the lower-boiling portion only hexenoic acid is isolated.

Based on the quantity of the formation of the anhydride (VI) and hexenoic acid (VIII), it is found that in the initial condensation of the dibromide, (III) is formed to the extent of about 15 to 20%, and other products constitute the major fraction to the extent of about 40% of the theory.

Some preliminary experiments were carried out to utilise the Diels-Alder reaction between ethyl sorbate and substituted ethyl acrylates to synthesise tetrahydroisophthalic acids, but in this case ethyl $\beta\beta$ -dimethylacrylate failed to act as a dienophile.

Since the C_{11} -acid contains three asymmetric centres, the synthetic and natural acids may be diastereoisomers because the asymmetric centre involving the methyl group has not been clearly defined in both the acids. Consequently, the next attempt was directed to the synthesis, according to the following scheme, of the C_{11} -dehydro acid. The constitution of the dehydro-acid has been suggested as (IX) from its mode of formation from the natural C_{11} -acid (Plattner *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1943, 26, 1553).

[X: R=Et; XI: R=H]

[XII: R=H; XIII: R=Me]

[XIV: R=Me; R'=Et;
XV: R=R'=H].

With this end in view, methylmagnesium iodide was allowed to react with ethyl α -propylidene-acetoacetate at a low temperature. Two fractions were isolated, the higher boiling one consisted of the hydroxy-ester (X) and the corresponding doubly unsaturated ester. From the lower-boiling fraction, the doubly unsaturated acid (XII) could be isolated on hydrolysis with alkali. On hydrolysis of the main reaction product, an oil was obtained containing varying proportions of (XI) and (XII), from which, however, (XII) was isolated. In one case, crystals of (XII) were obtained from the reaction mixture. The crude acid was dehydrated with *p*-tolylsulphonyl chloride at 130° - 135° and the doubly unsaturated acid was isolated as its methyl ester (XIII) on esterification with diazomethane. This ester on hydrolysis with alkali gave back the acid (XII) and took up two molecules of hydrogen on catalytic hydrogenation. The ester (XIII) was condensed with ethyl acrylate according to the Diels-Alder reaction at 230° - 240° in presence of a trace of hydroquinone to furnish (XIV) in about 30% yield. The unsaturated

acid (XV), obtained on hydrolysis, melts at 214-15°. It shows considerable depression in m.p. when mixed with the unsaturated acid isolated from cedrene. On catalytic reduction, it leads to a mixture of saturated acids from which no particular component could be isolated in pure condition. The mixture of saturated acids afforded an anhydride as an oil which solidified in the cold.

With a fair degree of certainty these experimental results may be explained on the basis that the C₁₁-acid cannot be represented by the cyclohexane derivative (I). Consequently it becomes of interest to synthesise the corresponding cyclopentane derivative (II), which is considered the only other alternative structure of C₁₁-acid; some preliminary experiments in this direction are recorded here.

The most obvious method appeared to be the condensation of the two following components according to Michael, but the condensation failed to proceed to any appreciable extent (cf. Bhattacharyya, this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 214).

Another attractive scheme appeared to be the condensation of ethyl α -bromoisobutyrate with the above cyclopentanone ester. The condensation did not proceed in the desired direction. Later on, detailed studies were carried out of this reaction in this laboratory with interesting results (Talukdar and Bagchi, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 20, 25).

EXPERIMENTAL

2:2:4-Trimethyl-1:3-dicyanohexahydroisophthalimide (III).—Sodium (7.3 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (96 c.c.) and to the cooled solution was added α,α' -dicyano- $\beta\beta$ -dimethylglutarimide (19 g., Vogel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1760) and refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. Refluxing was continued for about 8 hours after adding 1:3-dibromobutane (22 g.) and then it was poured into water (600 c.c.) containing HNO₃ (20 c.c.). An oil separated which gradually solidified; on standing in the cold, the solution became full of crystals. It was filtered and it weighed 16 g. It was crystallised repeatedly from methanol and acetic acid till the m. p. became constant at 160-61°; yield 1.2 g. (Found: C 63.59; H, 6.09; N, 17.26. C₁₂H₁₅O₂N₂ requires C, 63.66; H, 6.16; N, 17.20 per cent).

2:2:6-Trimethylcyclohexyl-1:1:3:3-tetracarboxylic Acid (V).—The above imide (1 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing for 48 hours with NaOH (2.5 g.) in water (20 c.c.). The solution was acidified and extracted repeatedly with ethyl acetate. On removal of the solvent, an oil remained which solidified in needles, m.p. 90°-102°, yield 1 g. It was

free from nitrogen. It was repeatedly crystallised from a mixture of acetone and benzene, when the m.p. rose to 119-22° with previous softening at about 100°. (Found: C, 51.95; H, 6.52. $C_{13}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 51.6; H, 5.9 per cent).

Anhydride of 2:2:6-trimethylcyclohexyl-1:3-dicarboxylic Acid (VI).—The above crude tetracarboxylic acid (1 g.) was decarboxylated at 200°-210° for 15 minutes. The residue was then refluxed with acetic anhydride (2 c.c.) for 2 hours and distilled in vacuum. The anhydride passed over at 91-93°/0.2 mm., yield 260 mg. (Found: C, 67.17; H, 8.39. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 67.32; H, 8.22 per cent).

2:2:6-Trimethylcyclohexyl-1:3-dicarboxylic Acid (I).—The above anhydride (100 mg.) was heated with 2*N*-NaOH solution (2 c.c.) on the water-bath for 10 minutes. On acidification the acid separated as an oil, which solidified to needle-shaped crystals on cooling in a freezing mixture. The acid (300 mg.) yielded the *p*-bromophenacyl derivative (470 mg., m.p. 70°), which on recrystallisation from alcohol melted at 74-75°. The sample was dried at 50° in high vacuum for 24 hours for analysis. (Found: C, 53.6; H, 4.9; Br, 26.6. $C_{27}H_{26}O_8Br_2$ requires C, 53.3; H, 4.64; Br, 26.3 per cent).

The combined mother-liquor, after separation of (III) through crystallisation, was diluted with water and the crystals were collected. This product (4 g.) was hydrolysed with NaOH (6 g.) in water (55 c.c.) by refluxing for 40 hours. It was repeatedly extracted with ethyl acetate after acidification; the solid residue left on removal of the solvent was decarboxylated at 200°-210°, and next treated with acetic anhydride in the usual way. On distillation, a fraction (0.85 g.) was obtained boiling at 50°-60°/0.1 mm. and another fraction (0.3 g.) boiling at 96-95°/0.1 mm. The second fraction was found to be identical with the anhydride (VI), as shown by the following analysis and by conversion into the low-melting needle-shaped crystals of the dicarboxylic acid (I). (Found: C, 67.32; H, 8.36. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 67.32; H, 8.22 per cent).

Δ²-Hexenoic Acid (VIII).*—The lower-boiling fraction (1 g.) was heated with 10% NaOH solution (5 c.c.) on the water-bath and the clear solution was acidified and extracted with ether. On distillation a clear oil (0.6 g.) passed over at 60°/0.1 mm. It developed a yellow colour with tetranitromethane. This acid (1.2 g.) took hydrogen (245 c.c.) in 20 minutes in acetic acid solution in presence of platinum oxide catalyst (calc. for one double bond, 240 c.c.). The anilide was prepared in the usual way from the unsaturated acid, which on crystallisation from ethyl acetate and petroleum ether (after decolorisation with charcoal) melted at 84-86° (lit. m.p. 87°). No isomeric anilide could be detected in the mother-liquor. (Found: C, 76.13; H, 9.95. $C_{12}H_{18}ON$ requires C, 76.15; H, 9.99 per cent).

Hexoic Acid.—The reduced acid, obtained above distilled at 60°/0.15 mm. It solidified when cooled in a freezing mixture (lit. -1.5°). The anilide, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from dilute methanol and melted at 92°, alone or with an authentic specimen. (Found: C, 75.38; H, 8.92. $C_{12}H_{17}ON$ requires C, 75.35; H, 8.96 per cent).

Ethyl 2-isopropyliden-3-hydroxyisovalerate (X).—Ethyl isopropylidene-acetoacetate (46 g., 114-15°/21 mm. or 104-105°/15 mm.), dissolved in petroleum ether (200 c.c.),

was treated with stirring at -6° to -12° with a Grignard's solution prepared from magnesium (7.5 g.) and methyl iodide (50 g.). At first there was a vigorous reaction. After the addition was complete, it was stirred for another hour till the temperature rose to zero degree. The dark oily liquid together with the yellow solid complex was decomposed with a saturated solution of ammonium chloride and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried and distilled. The first fraction was collected up to $108^{\circ}/16$ mm. (14 g.) and the second fraction (28 g.) boiling at $112-18^{\circ}/16$ mm. was again distilled, when it passed over at $113-16^{\circ}/16$ mm. as a light yellow mobile oil, yield 22 g. (Found: C, 66.31; H, 9.25. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 64.49; H, 9.74 per cent. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 71.39; H, 9.19 per cent).

2-isoPropyliden- β -hydroxyisovaleric Acid (XI).—The above ester (5 g.) was refluxed for 2 hours with 10% KOH solution (50 c.c.). The unchanged oil was removed with ether and the alkaline solution was acidified and extracted with ether overnight. On removal of the solvent, an oil (3 g.) remained which partly solidified. The crystals were collected (0.6 g.) and washed with ether. On two crystallisations from ethyl acetate, it melted at $132-33^{\circ}$ with evolution of a gas. (Found: C, 60.55; H, 8.31. $C_8H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 60.74; H, 8.91 per cent).

On hydrogenation in acetic acid solution in presence of platinum oxide catalyst, the compound took 1.1 moles of hydrogen.

2-isoPropyliden- β -methylvinylacetic Acid (XII).—The crude oil (3 g.), obtained from the above hydrolysis, was heated for 15 minutes at 130° - 140° with *p*-tolylsulphonyl chloride (30 mg.). On cooling, water was added when the crystals melting at $45-48^{\circ}$ separated out. This was twice crystallised from methanol containing a little water. It was obtained in stout plates, m.p. $51-52^{\circ}$, yield 2 g. (Found: C, 68.48; H, 8.65. $C_8H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 68.54; H, 8.63 per cent). 0.22 g. of the substance took hydrogen (76 c.c.) corresponding to two double bonds (calc., 70 c.c.).

Methyl 2-isoPropyliden- β -methylvinylacetate (XIII).—The crude oily product (3 g.), obtained above on heating with *p*-tolylsulphonyl chloride, was taken up in ether and esterified with an ethereal solution of diazomethane until a slight yellow colour persisted. On distillation, the desired ester (2 g.) was obtained as a clear colorless oil of b.p. $60-62^{\circ}/11$ mm. together with a higher-boiling fraction (0.3 g.), b.p. $108-10^{\circ}/18$ mm. (Found: C, 69.98; H, 9.02. $C_9H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 70.10; H, 9.15 per cent).

Methylethyl 1:3:3-Trimethyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexenyl-2:4-dicarboxylate (XIV).—The above diene ester (3 g.) and ethyl acrylate (2.5 g.) and a pinch of hydroquinone were heated in a sealed tube at 230° - 240° for 40 hours, in a bomb tube, half-filled with water. The mass became brown and was distilled, when a little of the diene ester (1 g.) was recovered together with the desired product (1.7 g) boiling at 100° - $120^{\circ}/0.1$ mm., and a resin remained in the flask. The higher-boiling fraction was redistilled when it passed over at $103-105^{\circ}/0.2$ mm., yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 66.18; H, 8.56. $C_{14}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 66.11; H, 8.72 per cent).

1:3:3-Trimethyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexenyl-2:4-dicarboxylic Acid (XV).—KOH (0.6 g.) was dissolved in methanol (3 c.c.) and to this was added the above ester (0.4 g.) and

refluxed for 24 hours under nitrogen atmosphere. It was diluted with water, the alcohol removed on the water-bath, and acidified, when a gum separated which gradually crystallised out. It was twice crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 214-15°. When mixed with the unsaturated acid from cedrene, it melted at 167-73°. (Found: C, 61.88; H, 7.86. $C_{11}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 62.25; H, 7.60 per cent).

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SESQUITERPENES AND RELATED SUBSTANCES. PART V. SYNTHESIS OF ISOMERIC METHYL_{iso}PROPYL_{cyclo}HEPTANONES*

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Synthesis of 2-methyl-5-isopropyl- and 2-isopropyl-5-methylcycloheptanones has been described. These ketones are expected to be of use in the synthesis of substituted azulenes.

For the synthesis of substituted azulenes, S-guaiazulene (I) and Se-guaiazulene (II), isolated from naturally occurring sesquiterpenes, the alkylated cycloheptanones constitute important intermediates. The distribution of alkyl residues in (I) and (II) has finally been confirmed by synthesis (Plattner *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1949, 32, 2137; Pliva *et al.*, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Com.*, 1951, 16, 158).

In the structural framework of carvone (III) and menthone (IV), the methyl and isopropyl groups are properly distributed and these may serve as convenient starting materials to realise the synthesis of these important azulenes. By applying the usual ring-expansion methods to these ketones, seven-membered ring ketones have been synthesised, but the constitution of these ketones could not be definitely settled in view of the alternative structures, possible from theoretical considerations (cf. H.C. Neumann, Dissertation, E.T.H., Zürich, 1949). It has been thought desirable to devise other methods for the synthesis of the seven-membered ketones from carvone and menthone, which will leave no ambiguity so far as the constitution of the final products is concerned.

* This investigation was carried out in 1948-49 during the tenure of a Foreign Travelling Fellowship awarded by the University of Calcutta in 1947 and constituted a part of the report submitted to the University.